

ISic3330

I.Sicily inscription 3330

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material**Object****Editor**

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2008.09.30

Last Change

2018-07-03 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based upon autopsy

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found during excavations by Caretoni, summer 1956, in trenches (VI and XXXI) on the east side of the 'portico orientale' which borders the east side of the 'agora inferiore'

Coordinates

37.998025, 14.263145

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Letter Forms

Text

Apparatus

IEPΩ, Facella 2006: 178 n.127

Translation

Commentary

It is not possible to expand the text of block (a): Facella (2006: 178 n.127) suggests that an iota can be read before the epsilon, but this is only the line of breakage on the stone, and his suggestion to read the name Hieron (i.e. King Hieron II of Syracuse, c.269-215 BC), if the monumentalisation of the agora belongs in the second century BC, is unlikely (if tempting). Campagna (2007: 117-118; followed by Prestianni Giallombardo 2012: 190 n.35) plausibly suggests that (b) should be restored to read [--έ]κ τῶν χ[ρημάτων--] ('from the funds...'), i.e. a reference to the financing of the building operation. In other words, the blocks may reasonably be imagined to form part of the dedicatory inscription of whatever structure was supported by the monumental 'muro a bugnato' which borders the west side of the principal street (the 'cardo massimo') as it runs north of the agora (and perhaps marks the eastern limit of the area of the so-called 'agora inferiore'), since the blocks were found in proximity to this wall. The letter forms are consistent with (but do not require) a date in the second century BC.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645581

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 303 no.3 fig.42, 311 no.12a

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Tigano, G. 2008. Il sito archeologico. In Scibona, G., Tigano, G.(eds.), *Alesa Archonidea. Guida all'antiquarium*. Palermo. pp. 71-90. At 86 fig.22-23

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